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TRAVELLING UNIVERSITY SEMINAR
SHARING KNOWLEDGE ON THE
INTANGIBLE CULTURAL HERITAGE
OF SOUTHEASTERN EUROPE

ROAD TRIP TO KNOWLEDGE

1
Volume

CONFERENCE PAPERS

THIS EVENT IS PART OF AN OPERATING PLAN OF REGIONAL CENTER
FOR THE SAFEGUARDING OF INTANGIBLE CULTURAL HERITAGE
IN SOUTH-EASTERN EUROPE UNDER THE AUSPICES OF UNESCO

1

EDIRNE
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ЗА ЕВРОПЕЙСКИТЕ
УНИВЕРСИТЕТИ

**TRAVELLING UNIVERSITY SEMINAR
SHARING KNOWLEDGE
ON THE INTANGIBLE CULTURAL
HERITAGE OF SOUTHEASTERN EUROPE
Edirne, Turkey, 2016**

CONFERENCE PAPERS

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Diana Stoyanova
Sofia Vasileva
Evgeny Velev

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**ЗА БУКВИТЕ
О ПИСМЕНЕХЪ**

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**THE NEWLY-OPENED REGIONAL CENTRE
FOR INTANGIBLE CULTURAL HERITAGE
IN SOFIA UNDER UNESCO – AN EXAMPLE
FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT
AND COOPERATION AMONG
THE COUNTRIES OF SOUTHEASTERN
EUROPE**

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Even the Preamble to the UNESCO Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage¹ emphasizes the fact that in society today comes to the fore the need of deep awareness, especially by the new generation, of the significance of the intangible cultural heritage and its safeguarding. All this can happen through combining the efforts in this direction of people of different types, state or public formations and separate individuals. That's why the appeal is towards active

¹ UNESCO Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage (Convention 2003), meeting in Paris, from 29 September to 17 October 2003, at its 32nd session <http://www.unesco.org/culture/ich/index.php?lg=en&pg=00006>

involvement and directing the attention towards the issue among the three major factors for the development of the processes related to the safeguarding of the intangible cultural heritage. Amongst the factors is the policy and the strategic vision of UNESCO aiming to disclose the place and the role of: state parties of the convention; communities, groups and physical entities; NGOs, experts, specialized centres and institutes².

In their operative directives on the implementation of the aims of Convention 2003 UNESCO advocates the idea to open in different points the so-called coordination units, which will encourage and assist the processes of realization of the policy of the organization for the safeguarding and popularizing the world's intangible cultural heritage.

The creation of such Centres is part of the strategy of UNESCO towards creating working plans, regular exchange of information on the different programmes, development and consistent inclusion of the local authorities, so as to improve the efficiency and the capacity at a national and regional level as far as

² Implementing the Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage at the national level. Training and capacity-building materials for a five-day workshop. UNESCO, 2011, p. 277-279;

achieving the aims of the organization is concerned³.

The regional centres for the safeguarding of the intangible cultural heritage – category 2 under UNESCO are a specific type of organizations. After their establishment, they are commissioned to coordinate the activities in the field of intangible cultural heritage in several countries within the region or around the world. The establishment of the centres is implemented after a proposal on behalf of the governments of UNESCO countries and is considered legally valid after the signing of a special agreement between the respective country and UNESCO. The definition "Centre – Category 2" means that the newly-created organization is an independent entity in its essence; legally it is neither part of the structure of the founder-state, nor is it part of UNESCO structures⁴.

Disclosing the essence of the idea to create these coordination units-centres, UNESCO recommends creating partnership networks. Countries willing to be members of these centres should express their readiness for active participation for the attainment of mutual goals.

³ Culture Sector Strategy for category 2 institutes and centres // http://www.unesco.org/new/fileadmin/MULTIMEDIA/HQ/BSF/images/CI_T_strategy_final_01.pdf <25.09.2012>

⁴ Implementatsiya Konvencii UNESCO ob ohrane nematerial'nogo kulturnogo naslediya na natsionalnom urovne. Rukovodstvo dlya treninga. UNESCO, 2010, s. 139-140

That's why in this respect, centres – category 2 have been established in different spheres – science, art, the environment and culture. Currently there are 23 centres functioning with the status of Category 2. Most of them concentrate their activities in the sphere of culture and cultural heritage⁵. In the sphere of intangible cultural heritage so far there are 6 centres in total – in Peru, China, Iran, Japan, The Republic of Korea and Bulgaria.

During the opening of the 34th session of the general UNESCO conference (2007), President Parvanov publicly announced Bulgaria's intentions to work in the direction of creating a Regional centre in Sofia on intangible cultural heritage. The same idea was repeated in February 2008 during the second meeting of the Intergovernmental UNESCO Committee on intangible cultural heritage. The creation of such a centre in Southeastern Europe has been welcomed by all countries in the region. Support has been offered in this regard by the International Network of Experts, which has been included in the agenda of all conclusive documents from meetings in Softanbolu, Turkey (2008), Zagreb, Croatia (2009), Ramnicu Vulcea, Romania (2010). Support for this undertaking has been offered by the ministries of

⁵ Culture Related Category 2 Centres and Institutes - <http://www.unesco.org/new/en/bureauof-strategic-planning/resources/category-2-institutes/culture/> <25.09.2012>

culture of the countries in Southeastern Europe, who express their satisfaction in the meeting of Bucharest, Romania (2008) of the fact that Bulgaria will host a regional centre on safeguarding of the intangible cultural heritage under UNESCO.

After a long-standing activity on the 25th October 2010 at an official ceremony in UNESCO in Paris, the Minister of Culture of the Republic of Bulgaria Vezhdi Rashidov and the Secretary General of UNESCO Irina Bokova signed "An Agreement between the Government of the Republic of Bulgaria and the United Nations Education, Science and Culture Organization (UNESCO) on the Creation in Sofia (The Republic of Bulgaria) of a Regional Centre for Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage in the South-Eastern Europe under the Auspices of UNESCO (category 2)"⁶. Geographically, this comprises countries of South-eastern Europe like Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Greece, FYR of Macedonia, Moldova, Romania, Serbia, Turkey, Croatia, Montenegro and Cyprus. According to the approved specification the Centre is oriented towards: creating conditions for the application of Convention

⁶ Internet site of the Regional Center for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of the Countries of Southeastern Europe under the auspices of UNESCO <http://bg.unescocenterbg.org/view/news/37> <25.09.2012>

2003 in Southeastern Europe; increasing the capacity of the Member States in protecting their intangible cultural heritage; in coordination, exchange dissemination of information and promoting regional and international cooperation for the protection of intangible cultural heritage. The main objective UNESCO puts forward is associated with developing activities aimed at implementing the strategy of the cultural sector organization for the implementation of the Convention on the Conservation of Intangible Cultural Heritage⁷. On 16th March 2011 the Bulgarian Parliament approves a law on the ratification of the Agreement⁸.

According to established legal and regulatory framework with Decree № 53 of 2011 by the President of the Republic of Bulgaria this law is promulgated in the State Gazette, then enforced.⁹ Legally, the regional centre in Sofia was registered under the Bulgarian legislation - pursuant to the Act of a non-profit purpose. Although it is an independent legal entity, it is set up by state institutions represented by the Ministry of Culture and the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences. The main mission of the centre in

⁷ http://www.unesco.org/new/fileadmin/MULTIMEDIA/HQ/BS/PDF/Fact_sheet_ITH_Bulgaria_130113.pdf <25.09.2012>

⁸ <http://www.parliament.bg/bg/laws/ID/1132> <25.09.2012>

⁹ State Gazette, issue 26 of the 29th March 2011

the agreed upon its formation statute¹⁰ noted that it should "promote cooperation in the field of intangible cultural heritage at national, regional and international levels and implement initiatives for the preservation and promotion of intangible cultural heritage of countries in Southeastern Europe". (Art.5) The mission of the Regional Centre can be grouped in two main directions: Actively to promote cooperation in the field of intangible cultural heritage at national, regional and international levels; Initiation and implementation of initiatives for the protection and promotion of intangible cultural heritage of SEE countries through training, sharing best practices, etc. In this respect Bulgaria has highlighted a wealth of experience, which is based on numerous workshops, seminars and work actively implementing and promoting the UNESCO Convention on Intangible Cultural Heritage. The main tasks that the Centre should include in its activities are:

1. "To promote UNESCO Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage and contribute to its implementation in the sub-region of Southeastern Europe;

¹⁰ Statute of the Regional Center for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of the Countries of Southeastern Europe - category 2 under the auspices of UNESCO - <http://hg.unesco-centerbg.org/files/f279dfde882b4c1f6288e428293882e4.pdf> <25.09.2012>

2. To increase the participation of different communities, groups and individuals in the safeguarding of intangible cultural heritage in Southeastern Europe;

3. To expand the opportunities of the Member States of UNESCO in Southeastern Europe in the protection of intangible cultural heritage;

4. To coordinate, exchange and disseminate information on the protection of intangible cultural heritage in the sub-region;

5. To encourage regional and international cooperation for the safeguarding of intangible cultural heritage.

6. To support efforts to protect the elements of intangible cultural heritage of the region included in the UNESCO Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage and the UNESCO List of Intangible Cultural Heritage in need of urgent action;

7. To support and promote the establishment and strengthening of national representative lists of intangible cultural heritage and national lists of items in need of urgent action in the countries of the region;

8. To cooperate with the institutions involved in the study and safeguarding of intangible cultural heritage at local, national and regional level and to establish relations between them;

9. To support and participate in activities to prepare specialists in the field of intangible cultural heritage;

10. To make efforts to strengthen cooperation with UNESCO and the relevant similar institutions in other countries and regions." (Art. 6)

To achieve these objectives, the specific functions of the centre are specified as follows:

1. To promote and coordinate research practices in the safeguarding of elements of intangible cultural heritage existing in the countries of Southeast Europe, according to Art. 11, 12, 13 and 14 of the Convention from 2003;

2. To organize training courses on the following topics:

a) The Convention of 2003 and its operational guidelines;

b) various examples of policies including legal, administrative, technical and financial measures that encourage the safeguarding of intangible cultural heritage.

c) acquaintance with the publications of UNESCO for the identification and documentation of intangible cultural heritage and its application in research on location;

d) safeguarding of intangible cultural heritage through formal and informal education.

3. To broaden international, regional and sub-regional cooperation through the establishment of

business contacts with institutions working in the field of intangible cultural heritage and in particular those established under the auspices of UNESCO (category 2) in order to coordinate the activities, the exchange of information and knowledge for the safeguarding of intangible cultural heritage and promoting best practices.

4. The activities and programmes of the Centre are carried out in accordance with the Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of 2003 and in particular its goals, objectives and definitions. (Art. 7)

The regional centre in Bulgaria is structured on the principle of which other such centres in the world operate, and borrowed from the structure of UNESCO, consistent with current Bulgarian legal and regulatory requirements. The management bodies are the General Assembly (Assembly), the Board and the Secretariat. The supreme body of the centre is the General Assembly (Assembly), which includes: two representatives of the Government of the Republic of Bulgaria (Ministry of Culture, Ministry of Foreign Affairs) or their authorized representatives; representative of each Member States who have sent a notification to the Centre for membership in accordance with Article 12 para. 2 of the Agreement between the Government of the Republic of

Bulgaria and UNESCO and those who have expressed interest to be represented in the Council; Representative of the Director-General of UNESCO; Representative of the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences; Representative of the Bulgarian National Commission for UNESCO; up to two representatives of other intergovernmental organizations or international non-governmental organizations which may be granted a place by the General Assembly (Art. 18).

The General Assembly holds its meetings, which are regular and urgent, at least once a year. The powers of the General Assembly are: to amend the statutes of the Centre; to elect and dismiss board members; the right to decide on the opening and closing of branches; decide on transformation and termination of the Centre; To accept the report of the Board for the Centre; to decide on the amount of membership fees and property contributions of the regular members of the Centre; to decide on the acquisition and disposition of property owned by the Centre; to revoke resolutions of the Board and other organs of the Centre that contravene the law, the statutes or other resolutions of the General Assembly; to admit and dismiss members of the Centre; to approve long-term and medium-term programmes of the Centre; to approve the annual work plan and budget of the Centre, including the establishment plan; to review the

annual reports submitted by the Executive Director, including two-year assessment of the contribution of the Centre to the programme objectives of UNESCO; to adopt the rules and determine the financial, administrative and personnel management procedures of the Centre in accordance with the laws of the country; to decide on the participation of regional intergovernmental organizations and international organizations in the work of the Centre; to make other resolutions as required by the law (Art. 19).

Between two sessions of the General Assembly (Assembly), the main issues related to the operation of the centre are defined by its Board of Directors (Executive Board). By right, it includes representatives of the three founder organizations of the Centre, but there is a hypothetical possibility that it could be expanded in the number of representatives.

The powers of The Board are: to represent the centre and determine the extent of representation powers of the Chair and other members; To ensure the implementation of the resolutions of the General Assembly; to dispose of the assets of the Centre in compliance with the Statute; to prepare and submit to the General Assembly a report on the activities of the Centre; to prepare and submit to the General Assembly a draft budget of the Centre for each financial year; to determine the order and organize

the activities of the Centre; to provide management and protection of the property of the Centre; to adopt organizational and management structure, the procedure for appointment and dismissal of personnel, the salaries and other internal regulations of the Centre; to appoint liquidators upon closure of the Centre, except in cases of bankruptcy; to decide on participation in other organizations; to make resolutions on all matters which by law or under the Statute do not fall within the remit of another body; to propose to the General Assembly the admission or dismissal of members. (Art. 28) In operational terms, the main unit of the Centre is the Secretariat, which consists of an Executive Director and a number of experts in various fields. (Art. 32)

One of the main functions of the centre is to help build an extensive partner network of experts and committed people to the ideas of the 2003 Convention, who will encourage and promote the application of the texts of the Convention. To achieve this, the secretariat of the centre takes action in promoting the participation and the cooperation of Member States and Associate Members of UNESCO. At present¹¹ there are members in the network and active representatives of the following countries: [AL] Albania; [BG] Bulgaria; [CY] Cyprus; [GR] Greece; [HR] Croatia; [ME] Montenegro; [MK]

¹¹ 11th October 2012

Macedonia; [RO] Romania; [RS] Serbia; [TR] Turkey. Invited to attend and pending confirmation of membership in the Centre are: [BA] Bosnia and Herzegovina; [CY] Cyprus; [MD] Moldova; [SL] Slovenia.

To realize the ultimate strategic task oriented towards sustainable development and operation of the centre and connected with the construction of an active working partnership network, the following is being done:

– Encouraging and promoting national conservation practices of elements of intangible cultural heritage in countries of Southeastern Europe, according to Art. 11, 12, 13 and 14 of the Convention of 2003.

– Initiating and organizing training courses on the following topics: The Convention of 2003 and its operational guidelines; Different examples of policies including legal, administrative, technical and financial measures that encourage the safeguarding of intangible cultural heritage; Getting to know the publications of UNESCO for identification and documentation of intangible cultural heritage and their application in research in the field; Safeguarding of intangible cultural heritage through formal and informal education.

– Efforts to expand the international, regional and sub-regional cooperation through the establishment of business contacts with institutions working in the field of

intangible cultural heritage and in particular those established under the auspices of UNESCO (category 2) in order to coordinate activities, exchange of information and knowledge for the safeguarding of intangible cultural heritage and promoting best practices.

With regard to activities of the Regional Centre for sustainable development work is being done in several directions:

– Firstly, sustainable development is implemented through the promotion of continuous training, sharing best models and practices, exchange of data and information between the countries of Southeastern Europe and expanding the parameters of action to neighbouring countries and regions.

– Secondly, resistance in the work of the regional centre, as well as its ideas is reflected in the ongoing series of international seminars and conferences, whose theme is aimed at promoting and implementing the Convention of 2003 in Southeastern Europe.

The work of the Regional Centre in Sofia, aimed at sustainable development, finds its expression in a series of workshops, consultations with a number of institutions, building new partnerships directed towards institutional strengthening. Internationally, active contacts and partnerships are established with the Department of Intangible Heritage Secretariat of UNESCO; Regional

offices of UNESCO in Venice, Moscow, Tashkent and Almaty; National Commissions for UNESCO of the countries of Southeastern Europe.

In the longer term, the fundamental principles of the Centre and its corresponding strategic objectives towards sustainable development are:

– Implementation of strategic management and strategic planning related to the main mission of the centre – promoting the implementation of the 2003 Convention:

– to implement flexible and modern models for expanding the scope of business and creating new networks of partnership.

– to establish a qualitatively new method of efficiency in managing processes for training experts in the field of intangible cultural heritage.

– Developing campaigns related to training modules popularizing and promoting elements of intangible cultural heritage in the countries of Southeastern Europe.

VISUAL AND COMMUNICATIVE MODELS OF PRESENTATION AND REPRESENTATION OF INTANGIBLE CULTURAL HERITAGE

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Generally, visual communication can be defined as a form of communication where the main role is played by images, signs, symbols, conventional and unconventional visual practices, metaphors, hyperbolization, visual ideas and messages, etc. It has existed throughout all historical and cultural stages of the development of the human civilization. In the era of information society, however, it enters the daily life of every contemporary post-modern person and its role grows constantly thus becoming fundamental. With the development and introduction of information and communication technologies, in particular new media in various spheres of human activity, visual communication is largely iconized. The most common and widely accepted category in visual semiotics is that of the "icon" taken as "those characters that have a resemblance to external reality." The concept